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Inherited Morality and Ethical Conflict in *Arcane*: A Philosophical and Psychological Critique of the Greater Good

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Abstract:

This article analyses the moral complexities presented in *Arcane*, the Netflix adaptation of the *League of Legends* universe by Riot games, through the philosophical lenses of deontology and utilitarianism, as well as Object Relations Theory. Key characters such as Jayce, Jinx, Vi, Vander, and Heimerdinger a Yordle, were analysed to explore how ethical ideologies are embodied and transmitted through relational dynamics. Deontological ethics emphasize personal duty and justice, while utilitarianism in *Arcane* is often used to justify systematic exploitation in the name of greater good and progress. Object Relations Theory is used to analyse how both of these ethical frameworks are inherited and internalised through influential relationships. The study reveals a frequent pattern in which the characters' morals and decisions are moulded by their psychological attachments and personal histories, leading to the perpetual conflict between the cities of Zaun and Piltover. Finally, the paper argues that the series *Arcane*

critiques the limitations of both deontology and utilitarianism when it comes to real world applications, presenting the need for a more nuanced, inclusive, and relationally informed of morality, this interdisciplinary approach provides insights into how a character's ethical reasoning, trauma, and inherited values affect their motivations, making way for broader implications for moral philosophy and media studies.

Keywords: Deontology, Utilitarianism, Object Relations Theory, Yordle.

Introduction:

Media has had a profound impact on the society for the past few decades. It has influenced our beliefs, our worldview, and our behaviour to some extent. This dynamic force has evolved significantly, from traditional media such as newspapers and television to the dominance of digital platforms such as social media and streaming. This evolution has both advantages and disadvantages, as it changes the way we consume information and influence social trends. In recent times, the intersection of moral philosophy and media has emerged as a compelling topic for academic exploration. Serialized television offers complex narratives that reflect, critique, and reshape ethical frameworks in contemporary society. *Arcane*, the renowned Netflix series illustrates this trend. The series blends steampunk aesthetics with intricate character development to portray the deep socio-political divide present between the cities of Piltover and Zaun. *Arcane* deals with question of justice, power, and the pursuit of the “greater good” making it an ideal text for ethical analysis.

The study utilises Object Relations Theory (ORT), a psychoanalytic theory, that grew out of the work of early psychoanalytic thinker like Melanie Klein, Sandor Ferenczi, Harry Stack Sullivan, Karl Abraham, and Margaret Mahler. This theory explores the formative role of early relationships in shaping the individual's moral reasoning and emotional responses to

analyse the ethical decisions of characters such as Jayce, Jinx, Vi, Viktor, and Ekko, and how moral ideologies are not only enacted but inherited, challenged, and distorted across generations. While the groundwork for this theory is derived from the theories of development of the ego in Freudian psychodynamics, Object Relations Theory does not support the idea of biological drivers being the sole deciding factor in the creation of personality in adulthood, it instead suggests that a persons' pattern of relation to others in adulthood is influenced by the caregivers during infancy. Disciples of this school of thought believe that the caretaker's relationship with the child and the way they treat them is a crucial deciding factor in the formation of their personality in adult life. An adult who has experienced abuse and neglect from their caregivers often expect similar behaviours from others who remind them of their abusive and neglectful parental figure. The caregivers and other parental figures in the infant's life are termed as 'object'. Later experiences in life can rewrite these early patterns, but the objects influence creates a mark that often persists throughout life. Additionally, this paper utilises utilitarianism and deontology, two major ethical theories to analyse the ethical dilemmas faced by the central characters in *Arcane*, a series based on the universe of *League of Legends* by Riot games. utilitarianism, introduced by Jeremy Bentham, focuses on the on the consequences of the actions and aims to maximize collective well-being by any means possible, while deontology, introduced by Immanuel Kant, emphasizes duty and rules, judging the morality of an action based on whether it adheres to set of rules or duties, and the end does not justify the means. utilitarian ideas encourage actions that leads to greater good for the greatest number, although different varieties of utilitarianism show different characteristics, the basic idea remains the same, to maximize *utility*. Jeremy Bentham, the founder of utilitarianism, described *utility* as the capability of actions to produce benefits to those affected, be it monetary gain, welfare or preventing harm. deontological ideals are often in contrast to utilitarianism, as the theory supports that morality of actions should be based on whether those

actions itself are right or wrong under a series of rules and principles, rather than based on the consequences of the action. Kant the founder of deontological ethics argues that the consequences of an act of willing cannot be used to determine whether that person has good will or not, as actions causing harming to an innocent person could accidentally yield good consequences and vice versa. Instead, he claims, that a person acting out of respect for the moral law has good will.

Through this interdisciplinary approach, this paper seeks to demonstrate how *Arcane* emphasizes on the philosophical tension between duty and consequences as well as critiquing the idea of moral autonomy, revealing that ethical values are evolving constructs not chosen in isolation but in relation.

Vander is a central character of *Arcane* who played a crucial role in the beginning of the series as the guardian and leader of Zaun as well as the adoptive father of Vi and Powder. Vander exhibited strong deontological ethics, actions driven by duty-to the people of Zaun, to peace, and to his adoptive children. He takes a strict moral stance against violence as a means to end, despite being a revolutionary before the start of the series, Vander now prioritizes peace and stability for the people of Zaun over violent rebellion. Vander has two adoptive daughters Vi and Powder, both of whom were the children of his late best friend, Felicia, her death and his duty to protect her daughter become two of the many reasons why Vander decided to forgo violence. This stance of Vander shows his adherence to deontological ethics, where right action is dictated by duty and moral rule.

Vi, Vanders adoptive daughter takes after him, internalizing his moral code through her formative attachment to him. Vi's fierce loyalty, her sense of righteousness, and her protective instinct towards Powder, all reflect Vander's values. Her actions show a strong belief in doing what is morally right- even at personal cost. After powder's mess up which caused the death of

Vander and their friends, Vi still chose to rush back to Powder's side and protect her, showing commitment to her familial duty even when she is suffering herself. Her character and personality exhibited in the series wasn't created in a vacuum, after Vander's death Vi was thrust into a world where her values and principles were constantly tested by the harsh realities of the world. Vi affiliates herself with Caitlyn an enforcer of Piltover, a figure committed to institutional justice, contrary to Vi's sense of morality and justice, which is more attuned to navigating the lawless city of Zaun. Vi aligns herself with Caitlyn because they share a common desire, the pursuit of justice. Vi doesn't trust the system blindly, she is more focused on doing what is right within it. Vi refuses to join Silco's cause after spending many years in the prison of Piltover, her rejection of Silco's end-justify-means ideology shows that her moral code is still rooted in justice and duty. The importance Vander and Vi give to individual dignity and moral duty often puts them at odds with the greater good narratives, showing how the ethical responsibility towards individuals cannot be discarded in favour of abstract ideals. Vi embodies Vander's legacy by navigating a corrupt and fractured world with a sense of duty and unyielding justice.

Silco is a central character from the series *Arcane*, he was a criminal and a revolutionary who came into power as the leader of Zaun after the death of Vander, he also took in Vander's adoptive daughter Powder as one of his people, this led to Powder changing her name to Jinx, symbolising the death of her old weak self. Silco was Vander's sworn brother and partner in leading Zaun in the past, they brought structure and order to a once lawless place pit in the world. Silco favoured violence as a means to an end, which Vander didn't agree with due to his sense of moral code and duty to maintain peace. Vander tried to kill Silco due to a disagreement about how to achieve Zaun's independence from Piltover, Vander wanted to achieve freedom and peace through diplomacy and negotiation, while Silco was willing to use violence and

manipulation to achieve their goals. Silco's violent actions indirectly caused the death of their best friend, Felicia, this caused further rift between them.

After Jinx was taken in by Silco, his end justifies the means ideology becomes deeply internalized within Jinx. Silco becomes both a father figure and manipulator in Jinx life, internalizing in her mind the idea that her worth is tied to her usefulness. Despite being portrayed as an evil character, Silco cares a great deal about Jinx, though he is not great at showing it. Silco's affection towards Jinx is also due to her resembling his younger self. Silco's revolutionary ambitions, while morally ambiguous is rooted in his desire to bring about greater good for the people of Zaun. He seeks to create an independent and self-sufficient Zaun, free from the clutches of Piltover. However, his methods of utilising violence and manipulation as a means to bring about this change, raises questions about the morality of his actions.

Jinx's psychological trauma is deeply rooted in her losing her family and Silco's twisted care. Her actions are erratic and destructive often undermining Silco's political agendas, showing how her trauma is affecting her inherited ideologies. Jinx's ideologies are fractured as result of her attachment to Vander and Silco, both being her father figures with opposing ideologies, this apparent fracture in her ideologies causes her to be unpredictable and make contradicting choices throughout the series. Jinx's desire to protect Isha, her adoptive sister, even at the cost of sacrificing herself shows that Vander's ideology of familial duty exist within her. In the alternate universe where Ekko and Heimerdinger are sent to, Powder is a kind person who is more interested in scientist discoveries and creating stuff rather than revelling in destruction. This is due to her family and friends except for Vi, who died protecting her, still being alive. With the presence of familial bonds which helped her process the trauma of losing her sister combined with the absence of an opposing ideology within her conscience, Powder turnout as a completely different person in the alternate timeline.

Heimerdinger is a Yordle character in the animated series *Arcane*, he is known for being an inventor, scientist, and professor in the city of Piltover. He is also a respected member of the Piltover council that regulates the working of Piltover, though he is only interested in the matters regarding new inventions and not concerned with the political aspect of it, making him oblivious to the darker sides of it, mainly their dealing in regarding to the undercity Zaun. Heimerdinger played a crucial role in the creation of *Hextech* as the mentor of Jayce, he also became the mentor of Ekko in the latter part of the series. Heimerdinger embodies a cautious and idealistic utilitarianism, relentless in his pursuit of scientific Advancement and greater good. As Jayce's mentor Heimerdinger imparts his belief that scientific advancement should never occur at the cost of human life, this becomes a baseline for Jayce's ethical views regarding his role as both an inventor and a citizen of Piltover.

Jayce is driven by his desire to harness magic with the help of science, this is caused by an encounter he had with a mage during his childhood, the mage saved both Jayce and his mother from certain death during an ice storm. This event that occurred in his early age shaped Jayce's life's work which led to him abandoning his family business and pursue research into the arcane. After the creation of Hextech, Jayce gets more involved with the political side of Piltover's council gaining more and more political power, which led to his gradual shift from Heimerdinger's idealism to a pragmatic utilitarianism. This shift in Jayce was caused by Mel, another member of the council. Initially, she regarded Jayce as an investment and potential political ally, even though this sometimes involved manipulating him to achieve her goals. Despite his initial beliefs, Jayce supported the militarization of Hextech, believing it to be necessary to maintain peace and order. This shift in his beliefs shows how political pressure and ambition can influence and distort inherited ethics. Jayce's compromises are often justified as "necessary sacrifices," yet the burden of his choices fall upon the people of Zaun. His decision to build the hex-core deep underground to safeguard Piltover from a potential core

meltdown leads to the water supply of Zaun getting contaminated, an action taken to ensure the safety of one city inadvertently caused harm to the other.

Conclusion:

The series *Arcane* serves as a profound case study in the role of relation in the transmission of ideologies. By analysing the various mentor-disciple and parent-child relation present in the series, this paper shows how various ethical values are inherited by the characters through formative attachments and how those values are then reshaped by personal trauma, conflicting ideologies, and changing social contexts. It also sheds light on how one-dimensional moral ethics like utilitarianism and deontology alone cannot bring about true peace and justice, it requires a flexible mind which understand the harsh realities of the world. *Arcane* questions the moral coherence of greater good when it is pursued without empathy, personal accountability, and relational insight.

By utilising Object Relations Theory, we can see how figure like Vander, Silco, and Heimerdinger impart the foundational framework onto Vi, Jinx, and Jayce respectively. These inherited ideologies-rooted in deontological notions of duty and utilitarian pursuit of greater good aren't just absorbed passively, they get twisted and distorted by the complex moral realities. Jinx's slow descent in madness, Vi's unwavering sense of justice and familial duty, and Jayce's compromise of ethical values shows the chaotic nature and evolutionary potential of inherited moralities. *Arcane* provides a complex moral universe where greater-good is not an objective endpoint, but a contested, emotionally charged narrative shaped by who holds power.

Ultimately, *Arcane* critiques the notion of morality being a personal choice, Instead, it shows that the development of ethical values are often dynamic and relational in nature, deeply shaped by psychological interactions and external influences. This paper aims to show that a

person's moral values are not determined by abstract philosophical theories alone, but shaped by their connections, experiences, and losses. By doing so, it calls for a more nuanced understanding of ethics in both the fictional and real-world fractured societies.

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